

TEACHERS' MANAGEMENT AND FACILITATION SKILLS ACROSS SCIENCE DISCIPLINE IN BANAYBANAY DISTRICT

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Abstract.

The study unfolded the extent of Teachers' management and facilitation skills across science discipline in Banaybanay District Schools, Davao Oriental Schools Division. The study used non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, where it utilized adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected teacher-respondents. Data gathered were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that teachers' management across science discipline in terms of communication, assessment and feedback, subject knowledge, planning and organization, technology integration, classroom management and differentiation is moderately extensive, while, teachers' facilitation skills across science discipline in terms of inquiry-based learning, scaffolding and guided discovery, facilitating collaborative learning, encouraging critical thinking, cultivating scientific creativity and questioning technique is extensive. There is a significant relationship between teachers' management and facilitation skills across science discipline. Domains of teachers' management in terms of subject knowledge, planning and organization, communication and technology integration significantly influence facilitation skills across science discipline. Future research may conduct research to evaluate the effectiveness of professional development programs that aim to enhance teachers' management and facilitation skills in the science discipline. Investigate the long-term impact of such programs on teacher practices, student learning outcomes, and overall classroom environments.

KEY WORDS

1. management 2. facilitation skills 3. science discipline

1. Introduction

Effective management and facilitation skills are critical for science teachers worldwide to provide quality education and foster students' scientific understanding and inquiry. However, there are several issues and concerns surrounding the management and facilitation skills of teachers across the science discipline at the international level. Teaching science in an international context involves navigating diverse cultural norms, values, and educational systems. Authors such as Hofstede (1980) emphasize the impact of cultural dimensions on teaching practices. Teachers need to adapt their management and facilitation skills to address cultural differences, language barriers, and varying levels of resources and support available in different

countries (Loucks-Horsley et al., 2003). Access to high-quality professional development and ongoing support is crucial for enhancing teachers' management and facilitation skills. However, many international contexts face challenges in providing adequate training opportunities and support systems for science teachers. Darling-Hammond (2017) highlights the importance of continuous professional learning for teachers to stay updated with best practices in science education. Insufficient resources, including laboratory equipment, technology, and teaching materials, pose significant challenges to effective management and facilitation in science classrooms (Wei, 2016). Teachers often struggle to conduct hands-on experiments, provide meaningful inquiry experiences, and engage students in authentic scientific practices due to limited resources and infrastructure. Effective assessment practices are vital for monitoring student progress and informing instruction. However, international contexts may face challenges related to standardized testing, limited assessment tools aligned with inquiry-based learning, and the pressure to focus on rote memorization rather than conceptual understanding (Liu, 2017). These factors can hinder teachers' ability to assess and provide meaningful feedback on students' scientific knowledge and skills. Teaching science in a language that is not the students' first language presents unique challenges for both teachers and students. Language proficiency issues can impact students' comprehension of scientific concepts and teachers' ability to effectively communicate and facilitate learning experiences (Yager, 2015). Teachers must employ strategies to scaffold language acquisition and ensure students' understanding of scientific terminology and concepts. Effective management and facilitation skills are crucial for science teachers in the Philippines to provide quality science education and foster students' scientific understanding and inquiry. However, there are several unique issues and concerns specific to the Philippine context. One of the primary challenges faced by science teachers in the Philippines is the lack of adequate resources and infrastructure. Many schools, especially in rural areas and economically disadvantaged communities, struggle to provide necessary laboratory equipment, technology, and teaching materials (Dizon Dumlaog, 2018). This limitation hinders teachers' ability to conduct hands-on experiments, facilitate inquiry-based learning, and provide authentic science experiences for students. In the Philippines, English is used as the medium of instruction in science education. However, many students have varying levels of proficiency in English, which poses challenges for both teachers and students. Teachers must navigate the use of English and local languages, often engaging in code-switching to ensure students' comprehension of scientific concepts (Esteban, 2015). This linguistic challenge requires teachers to develop effective strategies to facilitate learning and promote language acquisition. On the other hand, professional development opportunities for science teachers in the Philippines need improvement. Ongoing training and support are essential for enhancing teachers' management and facilitation skills (Nuqui Monje, 2020). However, limited access to professional development programs, especially in remote areas, hampers teachers' ability to stay updated with best practices and innovative approaches in science education. In addition Assessment practices in the Philippine education system often prioritize standardized testing and rote memorization over authentic assessment aligned with inquiry-based learning. The heavy emphasis on high-stakes examinations may lead to a narrow focus on content knowledge rather than fostering critical thinking, problem-solving, and scientific inquiry skills (Department of Education, 2018). This challenge requires a shift towards more holistic and authentic assessment practices that align with 21st-century skills. Socio-cultural

factors play a significant role in science education in the Philippines. The cultural beliefs, values, and traditions of students and their communities can influence their attitudes towards science and their perception of the relevance of scientific knowledge (Santos Pijano, 2017). Given such, Science teachers in Banaybanay District need to bridge the gap between the science curriculum and students' lived experiences by integrating local contexts and engaging the community in science-related activities. Thus, this study is conducted.

2. Methodology

This chapter contains the discussion of the methodical process in the conduct of the study. This includes the process in the selection of the design of the study, the respondents and its sampling method, the research instruments to be used in data gathering, the procedure, and the ethical consideration and lastly, the data analysis. These steps are considered essentials to assume appropriateness and correctness in the conduct of the methodical steps.

2.1. Research Design—Descriptive-correlational research design is a type of research that aims to describe the relationship between two or more variables. This type of research design does not involve any intervention or manipulation of variables but rather aims to determine the strength and direction of the relationship between variables. Descriptive-correlational research design is often used in social science research, including educational research, as it allows researchers to examine patterns and relationships among variables that cannot be manipulated for ethical or practical reasons. According to Creswell (2014), descriptive-correlational research design is used to describe and explain the relationship between two or more variables. The main goal of this type of research design is to identify the relationship between variables, and it can be used to make predictions about future events. Descriptive-correlational research design is often used in exploratory studies or when researchers are interested in establishing the existence of a relationship between variables. In this study, correlational research design can be applied to investigate the relationship between teachers' management and facilitation skills across Science discipline. The study can focus on the extent to which teachers have a higher level of science literacy have better science pedagogical skills. The study can also examine whether there is a positive relationship between management and facilitation skills. One advantage of using a correlational research design is that it allows researchers to investigate relationships between variables that cannot be manipulated or controlled, such as age, gender, and socio-economic status. This design is also useful for studying complex phenomena such as science literacy and communication, which involves multiple factors that can affect learners' performance. The correlation analysis can reveal whether a significant relationship exists between the two variables and the strength of the relationship. A positive correlation between management and facilitation skills indicated that teachers who have a higher level of science management are also likely to have better science facilitation skills. In conclusion, correlational research design is a suitable research design for investigating the relationship between management and facilitation skills. This design allows researchers to explore the complex interplay between different factors that can affect learners' performance in these two critical areas.

2.2. Research Respondents—Respondents of the study were the Junior High School Teachers of Banaybanay District Schools in Davao de

Oro Division. Using Raosoft sample size calculator, a total of 120 respondents were taken randomly from each respective Junior High Schools. Once randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platform and face to face considering the availability of the Wifi Connections, they likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study. As much as possible, these respondents are teaching Science in the respective schools to determine their management and facilitation skills, and how they function and contributed to the learning outcomes given new normal learning system during SY 2022-2023. Ethics of research and in the process of collecting survey responses were explicitly discussed with the respondents and even observance to health protocol was strictly implemented based on the Executive Order 31 S 2020, to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This research study used an adapted survey instrument. Items were adapted from the contents of the reviewed literatures. There are two parts of the survey

questionnaire which consists of the indicators of extent of management skills in terms of subject knowledge, planning and organization, communication, classroom management, differentiation, technology intervention and assessment and feedback. On the other hand, the second part of the survey is the extent of facilitation skills in terms of inquiry-based leaning, scaffolding and guided discovery, questioning techniques, facilitating collaborative learning, encouraging critical thinking and cultivating scientific creativity among Science Teachers in Bantayan District Schools. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at .05 level of confidence and generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.889 which means that 88.9 percent level of confidence of the validity and reliability of the survey statement constructs. (Pallant 2010).

The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of management skills of Science Teachers. Scale, descriptive rating and interpretation are provided below:

Descriptive Ratings of Management Skills

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The management skills are always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The management skills are oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The management skills are sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The management skills are rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The management skills are not manifested

Descriptive Ratings of Facilitation Skills

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The facilitation skill is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The facilitation skill is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The facilitation skill is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The facilitation skill is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The facilitation skill is not manifested

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—

The preceding statements explain the data gathering procedure steps where the researcher must comprehensively consider and follow. The statements are based on the policies and guidelines of the Rizal Memorial Colleges and the existing guidelines of the IATF to ensure safe and lower risks in the gathering of pertinent data. Permission to conduct the study. As early as January 2023, before collecting data, the researcher must obtain permission from the appropriate authorities, such as the research adviser and the Dean of the Rizal Memorial Colleges and the top management of DepEd Davao Oriental Division through channel. This permission-seeking process typically involves submitting a research proposal that includes information about the study design, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. The researcher provided information on March 2023 about the purpose and goals of the study, and how the data will be collected, analyzed, and reported. In addition, researchers must ensure that all participants are fully informed about the study and their rights, and that they provide informed consent before participating. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. Second week of April, the researcher ensured the accuracy and completeness of data, the distribution and retrieval of questionnaires should be conducted in a standardized and systematic manner. This involved the following conditions: Identifying the target population: The researcher identified the appropriate target population of the study, and ensure that the questionnaire is distributed only to individuals who meet the inclusion criteria. Obtaining consent: The researcher obtained informed consent from all participants before distributing the questionnaire. This may involve providing information about the purpose and goals of the study, as well as any potential risks and benefits. Ensuring anonymity and confidentiality: The researcher ensured that the questionnaire is anonymous, meaning that respondents are not identified by name or other personal informa-

tion. The researcher also ensured that the data collected is kept confidential and only used for the purposes of the study. Standardizing the distribution process: The researcher standardized the process for distributing the questionnaire, to ensure that all participants receive the same instructions and have the same opportunity to complete the questionnaire. Allowing sufficient time for completion: Participants were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaire, and were allowed to ask any questions they may have about the process. Collecting the completed questionnaires: The researcher collected the completed questionnaires in a timely and organized manner, to ensure that data is not lost or misplaced.

Collation and statistical treatment of data. Second week of April 2023, the researcher considered the following conditions that was followed for collation and statistical treatment of data as part of the data gathering procedure: Accuracy: The data should be accurate and free from errors. This means that the data should be checked and validated to ensure that it is correct. Completeness: The data should be complete, meaning that all necessary information has been collected. This is important because incomplete data can lead to incorrect conclusions. Consistency: The data should be consistent, meaning that there are no contradictions or discrepancies in the data. Inconsistencies can lead to confusion and inaccuracies. Relevance: The data should be relevant to the research question or problem being investigated. Irrelevant data can lead to incorrect conclusions. Timeliness: The data should be collected and analyzed in a timely manner. Delayed or outdated data may not be useful or accurate. Objectivity: The data should be objective, meaning that it is free from bias or personal opinions. This is important because biased data can lead to incorrect conclusions. Validity: The data should be valid, meaning that it measures what it is supposed to measure. This is important because invalid data

can lead to incorrect conclusions. Reliability: because unreliable data can lead to incorrect conclusions. The data should be reliable, meaning that it can be replicated or reproduced. This is important

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in number one (1) on the extent of management skills of Science Teachers, and statement problem number two (2) on the extent of facilitation skills of Science Teachers. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength / direction significant relationship between management and facilitation skills of Science Teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. Linear Regression analysis was used to address statement problem number 4, on the domains of management skills that significantly influence facilitation skills across Science disciplines of Science Teachers. All data processing and analysis were treated using the Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations then followed when results yield.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered. Tabular and textual presentation is presented to make more meaningful in the analysis and drawing out of implications. This further shows evidence to support the claim posed in the hypothesis.

Teachers' Management Skills across Science Discipline

Effective teachers' management skills across the science discipline play a vital role in creating a conducive learning environment and fostering student success. These skills encompass various aspects, including organization, communication, adaptability, and instructional strategies. Skillful science teachers excel in organizing classroom materials, lab equipment, and resources in a structured manner, ensuring easy access and efficient utilization. Moreover, they possess excellent communication skills, enabling them to articulate complex scientific concepts in a clear and concise manner, encouraging student engagement and comprehension. Additionally, adept science teachers exhibit adaptability by adjusting their instructional methods to cater to diverse learning styles and abilities, fostering inclusivity and promoting student achievement. They employ a variety of instructional strategies, such as hands-on experiments, demonstrations, and interactive discussions, to enhance student participation and critical thinking. Overall, teachers' management skills in the science discipline are instrumental in creating an engaging and effective learning environment that nurtures students' scientific curiosity and academic growth. Table 1 shows the extent of teachers' management across science discipline in terms of subject knowledge. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: teachers deliver accurate and up-to-date information to their students and involves staying abreast of the latest scientific discoveries, theories, and advancements in their specific discipline (3.55) and teachers engage in professional development activities to continuously enhance their subject knowledge and include attending conferences, workshops, and seminars, as well as participating in online courses or joining professional organizations related to their specific scientific discipline (3.40) are oftentimes manifested, while, teachers have a deep understanding of the subject matter they teach,

as well as the ability to explain complex concepts in a clear and concise manner, and be able to provide real-world examples and practical applications to enhance students' understanding and engagement (3.30), teachers have a comprehensive knowledge of the curriculum framework and be able to identify the essential concepts and skills that need to be covered (3.20) and involves fostering a spirit of inquiry and curiosity among students and encourage critical thinking, experimentation, and problem-solving skills to help students develop a deeper understanding of scientific principles and processes (3.12) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.31 denotes extent of teachers' management across science discipline in terms of subject knowledge is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 1. Extent of teachers' management across science discipline in terms of subject knowledge

No	Subject Knowledge	Mean
1	Teachers deliver accurate and up-to-date information to their students and involves staying abreast of the latest scientific discoveries, theories, and advancements in their specific discipline.	3.55
2	Teachers have a deep understanding of the subject matter they teach, as well as the ability to explain complex concepts in a clear and concise manner, and be able to provide real-world examples and practical applications to enhance students' understanding and engagement.	3.30
3	Teachers have a comprehensive knowledge of the curriculum framework and be able to identify the essential concepts and skills that need to be covered.	3.20
4	Teachers engage in professional development activities to continuously enhance their subject knowledge and include attending conferences, workshops, and seminars, as well as participating in online courses or joining professional organizations related to their specific scientific discipline.	3.40
5	Involves fostering a spirit of inquiry and curiosity among students and encourage critical thinking, experimentation, and problem-solving skills to help students develop a deeper understanding of scientific principles and processes.	3.12
Overall Mean		3.31

Science is a dynamic field, constantly evolving with new discoveries and advancements. Teachers must stay up-to-date with current scientific research and developments to effectively manage the science classroom. Authors like Bybee (2015) emphasize the importance of teachers' engagement in ongoing professional learning and their involvement in scientific communities to enhance their subject knowledge and management skills. Teachers' subject knowledge plays a significant role in managing diverse learners in the science classroom. Authors such as Lee and Luft (2019) highlight the importance of understanding students' prior knowledge, cultural backgrounds, and learning styles.

A comprehensive understanding of subject matter allows teachers to design differentiated instruction, tailor examples and explanations, and provide relevant contexts that resonate with students' experiences. Authors such as Magnusson, Krajcik, and Borko (2015) emphasize the importance of teachers' deep content knowledge in science education. A strong understanding of scientific concepts, principles, and processes enables teachers to provide accurate and meaningful explanations, anticipate student misconceptions, and guide effective classroom discussions. By continuously deepening their content knowledge, teachers can enhance their management skills in fostering student engagement

and promoting scientific understanding. The implementation of the K-12 curriculum in the Philippines emphasizes the integration of subject knowledge and skills. Authors like Nuqui and Monje (2017) highlight the significance of subject knowledge in aligning instruction with the curriculum standards. Teachers' mastery of subject matter enables them to design appropriate learning experiences, select relevant instructional materials, and assess student progress effectively. In the Philippine education system, subject knowledge serves as a critical component of teachers' management skills across the science discipline. By fostering conceptual understanding, aligning with the K-12 curriculum, addressing local contexts, promoting inquiry-based learning, and engaging in continuing professional development, teachers can effectively manage the science classroom. A strong foundation in subject knowledge empowers teachers to create meaningful learning experiences, nurture students' scientific understanding, and cultivate a passion for science among Filipino learners.

Table 2 shows the extent of teachers' management across science discipline in terms of planning and organization. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: teachers plan their lessons, ensuring that they are well-structured, coherent, and aligned with the curriculum objectives (4.10) and involves identifying the key concepts and skills that need to be covered, as well as determining the appropriate teaching strategies and resources to be used which includes selecting relevant experiments, demonstrations, and multimedia materials that will enhance student learning (3.40) are oftentimes manifested; while, extends to managing classroom logistics, such as arranging the seating layout, ensuring safety protocols are followed during laboratory experiments, and maintaining an orderly environment conducive to learning and establish

clear expectations and routines for students to create a structured and focused learning environment (3.35) and organize instructional materials and resources in a systematic manner, making them easily accessible to students which involve creating a digital or physical filing system for lesson plans, worksheets, handouts, and other teaching materials (3.00) are sometimes manifested, and involve assessing students' progress and providing timely feedback and design assessments that align with the learning objectives and provide meaningful feedback to students, helping them identify areas for improvement and further exploration, likewise keep records of student performance to track progress and adjust their teaching strategies accordingly (3.12) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.19 denotes extent of teachers' management across science discipline in terms of planning and organization is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Planning and organization are vital in implementing differentiated instruction strategies in the science classroom. Authors such as Tomlinson (2017) emphasize the need to plan for diverse student needs and abilities. By organizing instructional materials, grouping strategies, and assessment methods, teachers can tailor their instruction to accommodate various learning styles, interests, and readiness levels, promoting equitable access to science content. Effective planning and organization skills are crucial in managing instructional resources. Authors such as Rafferty, Raab, and Simmons (2020) highlight the importance of efficiently organizing and utilizing materials, equipment, and technology in the science classroom. Well-planned resource management ensures smooth lesson delivery, maximizes students' access to materials, and minimizes disruptions, contributing to effective classroom management.

Table 2. Extent of teachers’ management across science discipline in terms of planning and organization

No	Planning and Organization	Mean
1	Teachers plan their lessons, ensuring that they are well-structured, coherent, and aligned with the curriculum objectives.	4.10
2	Involves identifying the key concepts and skills that need to be covered, as well as determining the appropriate teaching strategies and resources to be used which includes selecting relevant experiments, demonstrations, and multimedia materials that will enhance student learning.	3.40
3	Organize instructional materials and resources in a systematic manner, making them easily accessible to students which involve creating a digital or physical filing system for lesson plans, worksheets, handouts, and other teaching materials.	3.00
4	Extends to managing classroom logistics, such as arranging the seating layout, ensuring safety protocols are followed during laboratory experiments, and maintaining an orderly environment conducive to learning and establish clear expectations and routines for students to create a structured and focused learning environment.	3.35
5	Involve assessing students’ progress and providing timely feedback and design assessments that align with the learning objectives and provide meaningful feedback to students, helping them identify areas for improvement and further exploration, likewise keep records of student performance to track progress and adjust their teaching strategies accordingly.	2.12
Overall Mean		3.19

Teachers’ ability to plan and organize their time effectively is essential in managing the science classroom. Authors like Hertzog and Klein (2016) emphasize the significance of prioritizing tasks, allocating instructional time, and maintaining a balance between content coverage and student engagement. Effective time management allows teachers to optimize instructional minutes, provide timely feedback, and create a productive learning environment. Alignment with the science curriculum is a critical aspect of teachers’ management skills. Authors like Segura and Verboeket (2016) highlight the significance of aligning lesson plans with curriculum standards and learning objectives. When teachers organize their instructional materials and activities in line with the curriculum, they ensure a coherent and meaningful progression of science content, supporting students’ learning and achievement.

Table 3 shows the extent of teachers’ management across science discipline in terms of communication. The result is focused on the

highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: teachers create opportunities for students to ask questions, express their ideas, and engage in scientific discussions through listening to students, teachers can better understand their individual needs and tailor their instruction accordingly (4.50) is always manifested, while, teachers are able to clearly and accurately convey complex scientific concepts and information to their students in a way that is easily understandable (4.00) and teachers use a variety of communication strategies to engage and connect with their students which include incorporating visual aids, multimedia presentations, hands-on activities, and technology tools to enhance communication and foster student engagement (3.40) are oftentimes manifested, moreover, teachers ensure that students understand the procedures, safety protocols, and expectations for conducting experiments, and be readily available to address any questions or concerns that may arise (3.38) and teachers provide updates on student progress, share re-

sources and strategies for supporting science learning at home, and address any concerns or questions that parents may have (3.00) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.65 denotes extent of teachers' management across science discipline in terms of communication is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive. Communication plays a vital role in facilitating collaboration among scientists, researchers, and educators. Scientists communicate their research findings, theories, and ideas to their peers through scientific publications, conferences, and presentations. Collaboration and communication enable the sharing of knowledge, expertise, and resources, leading to advancements in scientific understanding and dis-

coveries. Effective communication is crucial in science classrooms to convey scientific concepts, explain complex theories, and engage students in scientific discussions. Science teachers use various communication strategies, such as clear explanations, visual aids, demonstrations, and questioning techniques, to facilitate student learning and comprehension of scientific principles. Communication in the science discipline also involves scientific writing, which includes research papers, lab reports, and scientific articles. Scientists and researchers communicate their findings through well-written and structured documents, adhering to scientific standards and conventions.

Table 3. Extent of teachers' management across science discipline in terms of communication

No	Communication	Mean
1	Teachers are able to clearly and accurately convey complex scientific concepts and information to their students in a way that is easily understandable.	4.00
2	Teachers create opportunities for students to ask questions, express their ideas, and engage in scientific discussions through listening to students, teachers can better understand their individual needs and tailor their instruction accordingly.	4.50
3	Teachers use a variety of communication strategies to engage and connect with their students which include incorporating visual aids, multimedia presentations, hands-on activities, and technology tools to enhance communication and foster student engagement.	3.40
4	Teachers ensure that students understand the procedures, safety protocols, and expectations for conducting experiments, and be readily available to address any questions or concerns that may arise.	3.38
5	Teachers provide updates on student progress, share resources and strategies for supporting science learning at home, and address any concerns or questions that parents may have.	3.00
Overall Mean		3.65

Clear and concise writing allows for the dissemination of scientific knowledge to the broader scientific community and the public. Scientists and researchers communicate their findings through oral presentations at conferences, seminars, and workshops. Effective presentation skills, including clear delivery, visual aids, and engaging storytelling, are essential for effectively communicating scientific informa-

tion and capturing the audience's attention. In the Philippine setting, clear instructional communication is vital for science teachers. Authors such as Montilla and Ledesma (2016) emphasize the importance of using clear language, appropriate examples, and visual aids to facilitate effective communication. Clear instructions help manage students' understanding, engagement, and overall learning experiences

in the science classroom. Active listening is a crucial communication skill for teachers. Authors like Dela Cruz et al. (2019) highlight the significance of actively listening to students' questions, ideas, and concerns. Active listening allows teachers to address individual needs, provide relevant feedback, and foster a supportive learning environment. It also helps manage classroom dynamics and promotes student participation. Effective communication extends to collaboration and collegiality among teachers. Authors such as Tamondong et al. (2018) stress the importance of collaborative communication in professional learning communities. Engaging in open and respectful communication with colleagues promotes the sharing of ideas, resources, and best practices. Collaborative communication helps teachers manage their own professional growth and enhances the overall quality of science education.

Table 4 shows the extent of teachers' management across science discipline in terms of classroom management. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: implement strategies to address student diversity and individual needs in the classroom which include differentiated instruction, providing accommodations or

Effective classroom management in the science discipline encompasses various aspects such as establishing a positive classroom climate, implementing clear routines and procedures, managing student behavior, differentiating instruction, and organizing the classroom environment and resources. Effective classroom management in the science discipline helps teachers foster a sense of curiosity, collaboration, and critical thinking among students. It allows for the exploration of scientific concepts, hands-on experiments, and group discussions while maintaining order and discipline. By implementing effective classroom management

modifications for students with special needs, and fostering a culture of inclusivity and respect for all learners (4.00) is oftentimes manifested, while, involves managing time effectively and allocate sufficient time for different activities, including lectures, discussions, experiments, and assessments, likewise establish routines and transitions to optimize instructional time and minimize disruptions (3.38), involves creating a positive and conducive learning environment where students can actively engage in scientific inquiry and exploration (3.20) and establish clear expectations and rules for behavior in the classroom, emphasizing the importance of safety, respect, and active participation and consistent enforcement of these expectations helps maintain a focused and orderly learning environment (3.00) are sometimes manifested, and moreover, includes organizing the physical space to facilitate learning and arrange the classroom in a way that allows for easy movement, access to materials, and visibility of demonstrations and experiments (2.18) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.15 denotes extent of teachers' management across science discipline in terms of classroom management is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

strategies, teachers can create an environment where students feel safe to take risks, ask questions, and actively engage in scientific exploration and discovery. Teachers utilize classroom management strategies to facilitate the smooth flow of science lessons, maximize instructional time, and create a supportive and conducive atmosphere for scientific inquiry and learning. It involves setting clear expectations for student behavior, establishing consistent routines for science activities, managing laboratory materials and equipment, promoting active student participation, and addressing individual learning needs. Rivera and Basa (2018) highlight

Table 4. Extent of teachers’ management across science discipline in terms of communication in terms of classroom management

No	Classroom Management	Mean
1	Involves creating a positive and conducive learning environment where students can actively engage in scientific inquiry and exploration.	3.20
2	Establish clear expectations and rules for behavior in the classroom, emphasizing the importance of safety, respect, and active participation and consistent enforcement of these expectations helps maintain a focused and orderly learning environment.	3.00
3	Includes organizing the physical space to facilitate learning and arrange the classroom in a way that allows for easy movement, access to materials, and visibility of demonstrations and experiments.	2.18
4	Involves managing time effectively and allocate sufficient time for different activities, including lectures, discussions, experiments, and assessments, likewise establish routines and transitions to optimize instructional time and minimize disruptions.	3.38
5	Implement strategies to address student diversity and individual needs in the classroom which include differentiated instruction, providing accommodations or modifications for students with special needs, and fostering a culture of inclusivity and respect for all learners.	4.00
	Overall Mean	3.15

the significance of implementing effective classroom routines and procedures in the science classroom. Well-established routines and procedures for materials organization, transition times, and group work facilitate smooth classroom operations, minimizing disruptions and maximizing instructional time. Effective behavior management is crucial for teachers in the science discipline. Authors such as Quitaro and Montilla (2019) emphasize the importance of employing appropriate behavior management strategies. Proactive strategies such as clear expectations, positive reinforcement, and individualized support help manage student behavior and create a conducive learning environment. Lao and Maglasang (2015) stress the significance of differentiated instruction and individualized support in managing diverse learners in the science classroom. Adapting instructional strategies, providing scaffolding, and offering additional support to meet the varying needs and abilities of students help manage their engagement and progress in science learning. Creating an organized classroom environment is crucial for effective management in the science discipline. Authors such as Arayata and Bal-

lon (2020) highlight the importance of organizing resources, laboratory materials, and safety protocols. A well-organized classroom environment facilitates efficient lesson delivery, promotes student safety, and supports effective science instruction.

Table 5 shows the extent of teachers’ management across science discipline in terms of differentiation. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: use formative assessments to gather data on students’ strengths, weaknesses, and learning styles and inform the differentiation strategies they employ in the classroom., which understands each student’s needs, teachers can provide targeted support and challenges to help them progress in their scientific understanding (3.65) and extends to providing additional resources, enrichment activities, or advanced content for students who demonstrate a deeper understanding or a desire to explore beyond the standard curriculum which helps nurture their curiosity and passion for science (3.45) are oftentimes manifested, while, create heterogeneous groups where students with different levels of understanding and skills work

together on scientific investigations or projects which allows for peer support and the exchange of ideas, benefiting all students involved (3.15), involve modifying the content, process, or product of instruction and provide varied reading materials or resources at different reading levels, offer alternative explanations or demonstrations to cater to different learning preferences, or allow students to choose different modes of presenting their understanding of scientific concepts (2.60) and involves tailoring instruction to meet the diverse needs and abilities of students and recognize that students have different learning styles, backgrounds, and prior knowledge, and should adjust their teaching methods accordingly (2.55) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.08 denotes extent of teachers' management across science disci-

Differentiation allows teachers to tailor instruction to accommodate students' varying levels of prior knowledge, interests, and abilities. By offering different pathways and strategies, teachers can ensure that all students can engage with scientific concepts and processes effectively. Fisher and Frey (2017) explore the concept of responsive teaching, which involves adjusting instruction in real-time based on students' understanding and progress. Responsive teaching allows teachers to differentiate instruction by modifying their teaching strategies, providing additional support, or offering enrichment opportunities as needed. Wormeli (2016) discuss the importance of differentiated assessment in the science classroom. Differentiated assessment allows teachers to gather evidence of student learning using varied formats and criteria. It helps teachers understand students' individual progress, strengths, and areas for improvement. Providing timely and constructive feedback is an essential component of differentiation to support students' growth in scientific understanding. Differentiation is a crucial component of management skills for teachers across

the science discipline. By addressing diverse learning needs, adapting instructional materials, being flexible in approaches, implementing differentiated assessment, and fostering collaborative learning, teachers can optimize students' engagement and learning experiences in the science classroom. Differentiation supports students' scientific understanding, nurtures their curiosity, and promotes a positive and inclusive learning environment. Tomlinson and Moon (2013) emphasize the importance of differentiation in the science classroom to address the diverse learning needs of students.

the science discipline. By addressing diverse learning needs, adapting instructional materials, being flexible in approaches, implementing differentiated assessment, and fostering collaborative learning, teachers can optimize students' engagement and learning experiences in the science classroom. Differentiation supports students' scientific understanding, nurtures their curiosity, and promotes a positive and inclusive learning environment.

Table 6 shows the extent of teachers' management across science discipline in terms of technology integration. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: use sensors, probes, and data logging tools to collect real-time data during experiments, and then use software applications to analyze and interpret the data, helping them draw meaningful conclusions and deepen their understanding of scientific principles (4.00) and facilitate virtual collaboration among students. This enables them to work on group projects, discuss scientific concepts, and share ideas and findings, regardless of their physical location (3.45) are oftentimes

manifested, while, allows for enhanced learning experiences and promotes student engagement and understanding of scientific concepts (3.20) and integrate technology tools, such as interactive simulations, virtual labs, and multimedia resources, to provide students with hands-on experiences and visual representations of scientific phenomena that may be difficult to observe or replicate in a traditional classroom setting (3.10) are sometimes manifested, and while, allows for access to up-to-date information and

research which guide students to explore credible online sources, scientific databases, and digital libraries to gather information, conduct research, and stay updated with the latest scientific discoveries (2.15) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.18 denotes that extent of teachers' management across science discipline in terms of technology integration is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 5. Extent of teachers' management across science discipline in terms of communication in terms of differentiation

No	Differentiation	Mean
1	Involves tailoring instruction to meet the diverse needs and abilities of students and recognize that students have different learning styles, backgrounds, and prior knowledge, and should adjust their teaching methods accordingly.	2.55
2	Involve modifying the content, process, or product of instruction and provide varied reading materials or resources at different reading levels, offer alternative explanations or demonstrations to cater to different learning preferences, or allow students to choose different modes of presenting their understanding of scientific concepts.	2.60
3	Use formative assessments to gather data on students' strengths, weaknesses, and learning styles and inform the differentiation strategies they employ in the classroom, which understands each student's needs, teachers can provide targeted support and challenges to help them progress in their scientific understanding.	3.65
4	Extends to providing additional resources, enrichment activities, or advanced content for students who demonstrate a deeper understanding or a desire to explore beyond the standard curriculum which helps nurture their curiosity and passion for science.	3.45
5	Create heterogeneous groups where students with different levels of understanding and skills work together on scientific investigations or projects which allows for peer support and the exchange of ideas, benefiting all students involved.	3.15
Overall Mean		3.08

Technology integration allows students and teachers to access a vast array of scientific information, research papers, online databases, and educational resources. Digital platforms, such as online encyclopedias, scientific journals, and educational websites, provide students with the opportunity to explore current scientific discoveries, access multimedia content, and engage with real-world scientific data. This access to information broadens students' understanding of scientific concepts and fosters their curiosity

in the science discipline. Technology integration facilitates collaboration and communication among students, teachers, and the scientific community. Online discussion forums, collaborative project platforms, and video conferencing tools enable students to engage in scientific discussions, share ideas, and collaborate with peers locally and globally. Technology also allows students to connect with scientists, participate in citizen science projects, and seek expert feedback, promoting a sense of authentic science.

tific engagement. Lundin et al. (2018) stated that technology integration in the science discipline provides students with opportunities to express their scientific understanding creatively. Students can use multimedia tools, presentation software, and digital storytelling platforms to communicate their scientific ideas, present research findings, and create visual representations of scientific concepts. This fosters creativity, communication skills, and digital literacy, which are essential in the modern scientific landscape. It is important for teachers to consider effective pedagogical approaches and ensure thoughtful integration of technology into science instruction. By aligning technology use with learning objectives, providing appropriate guidance, and facilitating critical thinking and reflection, teachers can leverage technology to enhance the science learning experience for students.

Table 7 shows the extent of teachers' management across science discipline in terms of assessment and feedback. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: engage in self-reflection and evaluating their own work or that of their peers, students develop metacognitive

Feedback is information given to students about their performance or work with the aim of promoting learning and improvement. It involves providing specific comments, suggestions, or guidance on students' strengths and areas for improvement. Feedback can be both formal, such as written comments on assignments, and informal, such as verbal comments during class discussions. Effective feedback is timely, specific, and actionable, focusing on how students can enhance their understanding and performance. It helps students understand their current level of achievement, identify areas for growth, and make adjustments to their learning strategies. Assessment and feedback are

skills, gain a deeper understanding of scientific processes, and learn to provide constructive feedback to others (4.20) is always manifested, and, provide ongoing feedback to students and help teachers gauge their progress which can use formative assessments to identify areas of misunderstanding, adjust instruction, and provide targeted support to students as needed (3.50) and provide feedback on student work, experiments, or scientific inquiries, focusing on both the process and the outcome which helps students understand their strengths, areas for improvement, and guides them towards achieving the desired learning outcomes (3.45) are oftentimes manifested, while, evaluate students' knowledge and skills, such as written tests, laboratory reports, projects, and oral presentations which allows for a comprehensive and well-rounded assessment of students' scientific understanding (3.30) and provide valuable insights into students' understanding of scientific concepts and guide instructional decisions (3.20) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.53 denotes that extent of teachers' management across science discipline in terms of assessment and feedback is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

interconnected processes. Assessment provides data or evidence on student performance, while feedback uses that information to guide students' learning. Through effective assessment and feedback practices, teachers can support student progress, address misconceptions, promote reflection and self-regulation, and foster a positive and growth-oriented learning environment. Providing effective feedback is a critical aspect of science teacher management. Studies have investigated feedback strategies that promote student learning and growth. Sadler (2010) emphasizes the power of feedback in science education. Timely and specific feedback helps students understand their current level of achieve-

Table 6. Extent of teachers’ management across science discipline in terms of communication in terms of technology integration

No	Technology Integration	Mean
1	Allows for enhanced learning experiences and promotes student engagement and understanding of scientific concepts.	3.20
2	Integrate technology tools, such as interactive simulations, virtual labs, and multimedia resources, to provide students with hands-on experiences and visual representations of scientific phenomena that may be difficult to observe or replicate in a traditional classroom setting.	3.10
3	Allows for access to up-to-date information and research which guide students to explore credible online sources, scientific databases, and digital libraries to gather information, conduct research, and stay updated with the latest scientific discoveries.	2.15
4	Facilitate virtual collaboration among students. This enables them to work on group projects, discuss scientific concepts, and share ideas and findings, regardless of their physical location.	3.45
5	Use sensors, probes, and data logging tools to collect real-time data during experiments, and then use software applications to analyze and interpret the data, helping them draw meaningful conclusions and deepen their understanding of scientific principles.	4.00
Overall Mean		3.18

Table 7. Extent of teachers’ management across science discipline in terms of communication in terms of assessment and feedback

No	Assessment and Feedback	Mean
1	Provide valuable insights into students’ understanding of scientific concepts and guide instructional decisions.	3.20
2	Evaluate students’ knowledge and skills, such as written tests, laboratory reports, projects, and oral presentations which allows for a comprehensive and well-rounded assessment of students’ scientific understanding.	3.30
3	Provide ongoing feedback to students and help teachers gauge their progress which can use formative assessments to identify areas of misunderstanding, adjust instruction, and provide targeted support to students as needed.	3.50
4	Provide feedback on student work, experiments, or scientific inquiries, focusing on both the process and the outcome which helps students understand their strengths, areas for improvement, and guides them towards achieving the desired learning outcomes.	3.45
5	Engage in self-reflection and evaluating their own work or that of their peers, students develop metacognitive skills, gain a deeper understanding of scientific processes, and learn to provide constructive feedback to others.	4.20
Overall Mean		3.53

ment, identify areas for improvement, and make adjustments to their learning strategies. Feedback should be constructive, actionable, and focused on promoting deeper understanding of scientific concepts. Assessment and feedback inform instructional decision-making by providing valuable insights into students' progress and understanding. Science teachers use assessment data to identify students' strengths and weaknesses, tailor instruction to individual needs, and design targeted interventions. The findings from various studies highlight the importance of aligning assessment practices with learning goals and incorporating multiple forms of assessment to gain a comprehensive understand-

ing of students' scientific knowledge and skills.

Table 8 shows the extent of teachers' management across science discipline. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Communication (3.65) and Assessment and feedback (3.53) are oftentimes manifested, while, Subject knowledge (3.31), Planning and organization (3.19), Technology integration (3.18), Classroom management (3.15) and Differentiation (3.08) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.29 denotes that extent of teachers' management across science discipline is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 8. Summary of the Extent of Teachers' Management Across Science Discipline

No	Teachers' Management Across Science Discipline	Mean
1	Subject knowledge	3.31
2	Planning and organization	3.19
3	Communication	3.65
4	Classroom management	3.15
5	Differentiation	3.08
6	Technology integration	3.18
7	Assessment and feedback	3.53
Overall Mean		3.29

Effective management plays a crucial role in promoting quality science education and facilitating students' learning experiences. Authors such as Evertson and Weinstein (2015) emphasize the importance of implementing effective classroom management strategies in science classrooms. Their research highlights the significance of establishing clear expectations, maintaining a positive learning environment, and employing proactive strategies to prevent disruptive behaviors. By implementing these strategies, teachers can create an environment that promotes student engagement, active participation, and academic success. Building positive teacher-student relationships is a critical aspect of effective management across the sci-

ence discipline. Research by Pianta, Hamre, and Stuhlman (2012) suggests that strong teacher-student relationships are associated with increased student motivation, engagement, and achievement in science. Teachers who develop meaningful connections with their students create a supportive and inclusive learning environment that fosters academic and socio-emotional development. Differentiated instruction is a key component of effective management in science classrooms. Tomlinson and Moon (2013) emphasize the importance of tailoring instruction to meet the diverse needs and abilities of students. By employing differentiated instructional strategies, such as tiered assignments, flexible grouping, and varied assessments, teachers can

address individual learning styles and promote equitable access to science content.

Teachers' Facilitation Skills Across Science Discipline Teachers' facilitation skills across the science discipline play a crucial role in guiding and supporting student learning. These skills encompass a range of abilities that enable teachers to create an interactive and inquiry-based classroom environment, foster critical thinking, and facilitate meaningful scientific discussions. One important facilitation skill is the ability to pose thought-provoking questions. Effective science teachers ask open-ended questions that encourage students to think critically, analyze information, and make connections between scientific concepts. By asking probing questions, teachers can stimulate curiosity, engage students in active learning, and promote deeper understanding of scientific principles. Another key skill is the facilitation of hands-on experiments and investigations. Science is best learned through practical applications and first-hand experiences. Skillful teachers provide opportunities for students to engage in laboratory experiments, demonstrations, and other inquiry-based activities. They guide students through the scientific process, helping them develop essential skills such as hypothesis formation, data collection and analysis, and drawing conclusions. This hands-on approach allows students to actively explore scientific concepts, develop problem-solving skills, and cultivate a genuine interest in the subject. Furthermore, effective science teachers facilitate collaborative learning experiences. They encourage students to work in groups, engage in peer discussions, and participate in cooperative projects. Collaborative learning fosters teamwork, communication skills, and the sharing of diverse perspectives. Teachers create a supportive and inclusive environment where students can exchange ideas, challenge each other's thinking, and collectively construct knowledge. In addition to these skills, teachers who facilitate learning in the science

discipline also provide timely and constructive feedback to students. They assess student understanding, address misconceptions, and offer guidance to improve scientific reasoning and skills. This feedback serves as a catalyst for growth and empowers students to take ownership of their learning. Overall, effective facilitation skills in the science discipline empower teachers to guide students in exploring, questioning, and discovering scientific concepts. By creating an interactive and engaging learning environment, teachers facilitate the development of critical thinking, problem-solving abilities, and a lifelong appreciation for science.

Table 9 shows the extent of teachers' facilitation skills across science discipline in terms of inquiry-based learning. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: encourage students to work in groups, engage in scientific discussions, share ideas, and collaboratively analyze and interpret data which fosters the development of teamwork and communication skills while deepening scientific understanding (4.25) is always manifested, and while, encourages students to ask questions, investigate, and explore scientific phenomena which guide students through the process of formulating hypotheses, designing experiments, collecting data, and drawing conclusions (4.15) and promotes active engagement, critical thinking, and a deeper understanding of scientific concepts (4.10) are oftentimes manifested, meanwhile, offer scaffolded activities, prompts, or guiding questions to help students develop their scientific inquiry skills and navigate the investigative process effectively (4.00) and create opportunities for students to take ownership of their learning, make their own discoveries, and construct their understanding of scientific concepts which provide support, guidance, and feedback throughout the inquiry process to help students develop scientific thinking and problem-solving skills (3.50) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of

4.00 denotes that extent of teachers' facilitation skills across science discipline in terms of inquiry-based learning is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

Table 9. Extent of teachers' facilitation skills across science discipline in terms of inquiry-based learning

No	Inquiry-based Learning	Mean
1	Promotes active engagement, critical thinking, and a deeper understanding of scientific concepts.	4.10
2	Encourages students to ask questions, investigate, and explore scientific phenomena which guide students through the process of formulating hypotheses, designing experiments, collecting data, and drawing conclusions.	4.15
3	Offer scaffolded activities, prompts, or guiding questions to help students develop their scientific inquiry skills and navigate the investigative process effectively.	4.00
4	Encourage students to work in groups, engage in scientific discussions, share ideas, and collaboratively analyze and interpret data which fosters the development of teamwork and communication skills while deepening scientific understanding.	4.25
5	Create opportunities for students to take ownership of their learning, make their own discoveries, and construct their understanding of scientific concepts which provide support, guidance, and feedback throughout the inquiry process to help students develop scientific thinking and problem-solving skills.	3.50
Overall Mean		4.00

According to Harlen (2015), IBL promotes critical thinking by encouraging students to formulate questions, design experiments, analyze data, and draw conclusions. By engaging in hands-on investigations, students learn to evaluate evidence, make logical connections, and think critically about scientific phenomena. Harlen (2015) emphasizes that inquiry-based learning promotes critical thinking skills by engaging students in the process of scientific inquiry. When students are actively involved in formulating questions, designing experiments, analyzing data, and drawing conclusions, they develop the ability to evaluate evidence, make logical connections, and think critically about scientific phenomena. A study by Akpan et al. (2016) found that IBL in science classrooms increases student engagement and motivation. When students have the opportunity to explore scientific concepts through their own inquiries, they develop a sense of ownership and intrinsic motivation to learn. This engagement can lead

to a more positive attitude towards science and higher achievement. Akpan et al. (2016) conducted a study that demonstrated the positive impact of inquiry-based learning on student engagement and motivation in science classrooms. When students have the opportunity to explore scientific concepts through their own inquiries, they develop a sense of ownership and intrinsic motivation to learn. This increased engagement can lead to a more positive attitude towards science and higher levels of achievement. Research by Windschitl and Andre (2013) suggests that IBL helps students develop important scientific process skills, such as formulating hypotheses, designing experiments, collecting and analyzing data, and communicating findings. These skills are vital for scientific inquiry and prepare students for future scientific endeavors. Windschitl and Andre (2013) conducted a comprehensive review of research on inquiry-based instruction and found that it helps students develop important scientific process skills. These

skills include formulating hypotheses, designing experiments, collecting and analyzing data, and communicating findings. By engaging in authentic scientific investigations, students acquire hands-on experience with the scientific process, preparing them for future scientific endeavors.

Table 10 shows the extent of teachers' facilitation skills across science discipline in terms of scaffolding and guided discovery. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: provide support and structure to help students develop their understanding of scientific concepts (4.20) is always manifested, while, involve breaking down complex scientific concepts into smaller, more manageable parts, providing clear instructions and examples, and offering guiding questions to help students make connections and deepen

their understanding (4.00) and provide support and feedback as students engage in hands-on activities, encouraging them to make observations, generate hypotheses, and test their ideas through experimentation (3.50) are oftentimes manifested, and, release responsibility to students, allowing them to take on more independent and self-directed learning as they gain confidence and proficiency in the Science discipline (3.30) and approach scientific problems, think critically, analyze data, and draw evidence-based conclusions through modeling these practices, teachers provide students with a framework for their own scientific inquiry and discovery (3.10) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.82 denotes that extent of teachers' facilitation skills across science discipline in terms of scaffolding and guided discovery is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

Table 10. Extent of teachers' facilitation skills across science discipline in terms of scaffolding and guided discovery

No	Scaffolding and Guided Discovery	Mean
1	Provide support and structure to help students develop their understanding of scientific concepts.	4.20
2	Involve breaking down complex scientific concepts into smaller, more manageable parts, providing clear instructions and examples, and offering guiding questions to help students make connections and deepen their understanding.	4.00
3	Provide support and feedback as students engage in hands-on activities, encouraging them to make observations, generate hypotheses, and test their ideas through experimentation.	3.50
4	Release responsibility to students, allowing them to take on more independent and self-directed learning as they gain confidence and proficiency in the Science discipline.	3.30
5	Approach scientific problems, think critically, analyze data, and draw evidence-based conclusions through modeling these practices, teachers provide students with a framework for their own scientific inquiry and discovery.	3.10
Overall Mean		3.82

Scaffolding and guided discovery are instructional strategies that play crucial roles in the facilitation skills of science teachers. These approaches provide support and guidance to students as they navigate through challenging scientific concepts, allowing them to develop a deeper understanding and acquire problem-

solving skills. Scaffolding, based on Vygotsky's theory, assists students within their zone of proximal development (ZPD) to reach higher levels of understanding. A study by Dabbagh and Kitsantas (2012) emphasized the importance of scaffolding in science education, stating that it provides the necessary support and guidance for

students to successfully navigate complex scientific concepts and tasks. A study by Belland et al. (2018) explored the use of scaffolding in science classrooms and found that it enhances students' metacognitive awareness, leading to improved learning outcomes and a deeper understanding of scientific concepts. A study by Kim and Hannafin (2017) investigated scaffolding strategies in science classrooms and found that it encourages students to engage in discussions, share ideas, and collaborate on scientific investigations. This collaborative learning environment fosters the development of scientific communication skills.

Table 11 shows the extent of teachers' facilitation skills across science discipline in terms of questioning technique. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: gauge students' comprehension, identify misconceptions, and address gaps in understanding which allows teachers to tailor their instruction and provide timely support to individual students or the entire class (3.30), encourage critical thinking, promote active engagement, and deepen students' understanding of scientific

The questioning technique is a fundamental aspect of facilitation skills for science teachers. Effective questioning not only stimulates students' thinking but also promotes active engagement, critical thinking, and deeper understanding of scientific concepts. Effective questioning encourages students to analyze, evaluate, and synthesize information, thereby promoting critical thinking skills. A study by Tsai et al. (2017) found that open-ended and thought-provoking questions used by science teachers led to higher-order thinking and reasoning among students. By posing challenging questions, teachers can stimulate students to think critically and apply scientific concepts to real-world situations. Research by Tobin and Gallagher (2017) empha-

size that the questioning technique increases student engagement and participation in science classrooms. By posing questions that require active thinking and response, teachers encourage students to be actively involved in the learning process. This engagement leads to improved attention, motivation, and overall participation in scientific discussions and activities. Well-designed questions help students construct their own understanding of scientific concepts. A study by Cakmakci (2020) explored the impact of questioning techniques in science education and found that carefully constructed questions helped students develop conceptual understanding. By guiding students' thinking and encouraging them to articulate their ideas, teachers

Table 11. Extent of teachers’ facilitation skills across science discipline in terms of questioning technique

No	Questioning Technique	Mean
1	Encourage critical thinking, promote active engagement, and deepen students’ understanding of scientific concepts.	3.20
2	Involve asking open-ended and thought-provoking questions that require students to analyze, evaluate, and apply their scientific knowledge which encourage students to think deeply, make connections, and develop higher-order thinking skills.	3.00
3	Stimulate inquiry and curiosity in the Science discipline asking questions that prompt students to explore and investigate scientific phenomena, teachers spark students’ interest and foster a sense of wonder and curiosity about the natural world.	2.50
4	Gauge students’ comprehension, identify misconceptions, and address gaps in understanding which allows teachers to tailor their instruction and provide timely support to individual students or the entire class.	3.30
5	Encourage student participation and create a collaborative learning environment which invite students to ask their own questions, engage in scientific discussions, and provide explanations or evidence to support their ideas. This cultivates a classroom culture where students feel comfortable sharing their thoughts, debating scientific concepts, and collectively constructing knowledge.	2.10
Overall Mean		2.82

can help students make connections, identify misconceptions, and develop a deeper understanding of scientific phenomena.

Table 12 shows the extent of teachers’ facilitation skills across science discipline in terms of facilitating collaborative learning. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: promotes active engagement, teamwork, and the development of communication and critical thinking skills (3.50) and encourage students to value and respect each other’s contributions, fostering a positive and inclusive collaborative learning environment (3.40) are oftentimes manifested, while, guide and facilitate group discussions during collaborative learning activities, asking probing questions, encouraging peer-to-peer interaction, and providing guidance as needed which helps students develop their scientific reasoning, communication, and collaboration skills (3.30) and allows students to share ideas, discuss scientific concepts, and collaborate on problem-solving tasks (3.10) are sometimes

manifested, and establish guidelines for effective communication, respectful interactions, and the fair division of tasks which helps students develop skills in teamwork, negotiation, and problem-solving, which are essential for scientific inquiry and collaboration in real-world scientific settings (2.20) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.10 denotes that extent of teachers’ facilitation skills across science discipline in terms of facilitating collaborative learning is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Collaborative learning environments foster critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Research by Slavin (2015) indicates that when students work together, they engage in discussions that require analysis, evaluation, and synthesis of information. Collaborative problem-solving tasks encourage students to think critically, consider multiple perspectives, and develop effective strategies to solve scientific problems. Facilitating collaborative learning allows for peer learning and support.

Table 12. Extent of teachers’ facilitation skills across science discipline in terms of facilitating collaborative learning

No	Facilitating Collaborative Learning	Mean
1	Promotes active engagement, teamwork, and the development of communication and critical thinking skills.	3.50
2	Allows students to share ideas, discuss scientific concepts, and collaborate on problem-solving tasks.	3.10
3	Encourage students to value and respect each other’s contributions, fostering a positive and inclusive collaborative learning environment.	3.40
4	Guide and facilitate group discussions during collaborative learning activities, asking probing questions, encouraging peer-to-peer interaction, and providing guidance as needed which helps students develop their scientific reasoning, communication, and collaboration skills.	3.30
5	Establish guidelines for effective communication, respectful interactions, and the fair division of tasks which helps students develop skills in teamwork, negotiation, and problem-solving, which are essential for scientific inquiry and collaboration in real-world scientific settings.	2.20
Overall Mean		3.10

Facilitating collaborative learning is a crucial component of facilitation skills for science teachers. Collaborative learning environments promote active engagement, critical thinking, and effective communication among students, leading to deeper understanding of scientific concepts. Research by Johnson and Johnson (2014) highlights that collaborative learning promotes active engagement and participation among students. By working in groups, students engage in discussions, share ideas, and collaborate on scientific investigations. This active participation enhances students’ motivation and involvement in the learning process, leading to a deeper understanding of scientific concepts. A study by Gillies (2016) emphasized that collaborative learning experiences provide opportunities for students to articulate their ideas, listen to others, and engage in constructive dialogue. Through collaboration, students develop effective communication skills, including active listening, clear articulation of thoughts, and respectful exchange of ideas. A study by Webb et al. (2018) demonstrated that collaborative learning groups enable students to learn from each other through sharing knowledge, exchanging ideas, and providing support. Peer interactions within collaborative settings promote a deeper

understanding of scientific concepts as students explain and clarify their understanding to their peers. Collaborative learning experiences foster the development of social skills and teamwork. Research by Kagan (2019) emphasizes that collaboration in the science classroom enhances students’ ability to work effectively in teams, negotiate roles and responsibilities, and respect diverse perspectives. These social skills are essential for successful collaboration, both in academic and real-world contexts.

Table 13 shows the extent of teachers’ facilitation skills across science discipline in terms of encouraging critical thinking. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: fosters inquiry, analysis, and evaluation of scientific information and concepts (4.10) is oftentimes manifested, while, create opportunities for critical thinking by posing challenging questions, presenting complex problems, and engaging students in scientific investigations that require them to think critically and apply their knowledge (3.20) and encourage students to analyze and evaluate scientific evidence and data, supporting them in making connections between different scientific concepts and drawing well-reasoned conclusions based on evidence (3.00)

are sometimes manifested, while, involves promoting active inquiry and exploration which guide students to ask questions, propose hypotheses, design experiments, and analyze results, enabling them to think deeply and engage in the scientific process (2.30) and provide scaffolding and support to develop students' critical thinking skills in the Science discipline which offer guidance, ask probing questions, and challenge students' thinking, encouraging them to consider alternative explanations, evaluate the reliability of sources, and think critically about the implications of scientific findings (2.20) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.96 denotes that extent of teachers' facilitation

skills across science discipline in terms of encouraging critical thinking is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Research by Ennis (2016) highlights that encouraging critical thinking helps develop higher-order thinking skills, such as analysis, evaluation, and synthesis. By posing thought-provoking questions, presenting challenging problems, and engaging students in inquiry-based activities, science teachers stimulate critical thinking processes that enable students to go beyond rote memorization and develop a deeper understanding of scientific concepts. Encouraging critical thinking fosters improved problem-solving abilities among students.

Table 13. Extent of teachers' facilitation skills across science discipline in terms of encouraging critical thinking

No	Encouraging Critical Thinking	Mean
1	Fosters inquiry, analysis, and evaluation of scientific information and concepts.	4.10
2	Create opportunities for critical thinking by posing challenging questions, presenting complex problems, and engaging students in scientific investigations that require them to think critically and apply their knowledge.	3.20
3	Encourage students to analyze and evaluate scientific evidence and data, supporting them in making connections between different scientific concepts and drawing well-reasoned conclusions based on evidence.	3.00
4	Involves promoting active inquiry and exploration which guide students to ask questions, propose hypotheses, design experiments, and analyze results, enabling them to think deeply and engage in the scientific process.	2.30
5	Provide scaffolding and support to develop students' critical thinking skills in the Science discipline which offer guidance, ask probing questions, and challenge students' thinking, encouraging them to consider alternative explanations, evaluate the reliability of sources, and think critically about the implications of scientific findings.	2.20
Overall Mean		2.96

A study by Facione and Gittens (2016) demonstrated that when students are encouraged to think critically, they become better equipped to identify and define problems, generate creative solutions, and evaluate their effectiveness. By engaging students in problem-solving tasks, science teachers nurture their ability to apply scientific knowledge to real-world situations. Critical thinking encourages

students to engage in evidence-based reasoning. Research by McMillan and Halpern (2017) emphasizes that when students critically analyze evidence and draw logical conclusions, they develop a deeper understanding of scientific concepts and principles. By guiding students in evaluating the credibility and relevance of evidence, science teachers help them make informed judgments and engage in scientific

reasoning. Encouraging critical thinking nurtures scientific skepticism and inquiry. A study by Kuhn (2015) highlighted the importance of skepticism in science education and how it promotes critical evaluation of scientific claims and evidence. Science teachers who foster a classroom environment that values skepticism and encourages students to question and challenge ideas promote the development of scientific thinking and a deeper understanding of the scientific process. Encouraging critical thinking facilitates the transfer of learning beyond the classroom. Research by Perkins and Salomon (2018) emphasizes that when students engage in critical thinking, they develop transferable skills that can be applied to new contexts and disciplines. By encouraging students to make connections between scientific concepts and real-world phenomena, science teachers equip them with the skills necessary for lifelong learning and problem-solving.

Table 14 shows the extent of teachers' facilitation skills across science discipline in terms of cultivating scientific creativity. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: provide opportunities for students to collaborate, share ideas, and engage in scientific discussions through creating a classroom culture that celebrates diverse perspectives and encourages active participa-

Scientific creativity often transcends disciplinary boundaries, allowing for connections and integration across different fields. A study by Amabile (2018) highlights that cultivating scientific creativity can lead to interdisciplinary insights and advancements. Science teachers who encourage students to explore connections between science and other disciplines foster a broader perspective and inspire innovative thinking. Research by Cropley (2015) emphasizes that cultivating scientific creativity encourages students to generate original and innova-

tion, teachers inspire students to think creatively and build upon each other's ideas (3.40) is oftentimes manifested, while, foster scientific creativity by providing opportunities for students to engage in open-ended tasks, design their experiments, and explore scientific phenomena from different perspectives which encourages students to think outside the box and develop unique approaches to problem-solving (3.20), encourages students to think innovatively, explore new ideas, and approach scientific challenges with imagination (3.10) and create a supportive and safe learning environment that values and nurtures students' ideas and creativity which encourage students to take risks, embrace failure as a learning opportunity, and express their thoughts and hypotheses freely (3.00) are sometimes manifested, and while, involves incorporating hands-on experiments, inquiry-based activities, and project-based learning into the Science curriculum which allows students to explore their own questions, propose innovative solutions, and engage in scientific discoveries that spark their curiosity and ignite their creativity (2.10) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.96 denotes that extent of teachers' facilitation skills across science discipline in terms of cultivating scientific creativity is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

tive ideas in the scientific domain. By providing opportunities for divergent thinking, brainstorming, and problem-solving challenges, science teachers stimulate students' creativity, enabling them to approach scientific problems in unique ways and develop novel solutions. Cultivating scientific creativity is closely intertwined with critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. A study by Runco and Jaeger (2012) demonstrated that engaging in creative processes promotes analytical thinking, flexible problem-solving, and the ability to view chal-

Table 14. Extent of teachers’ facilitation skills across science discipline in terms of cultivating scientific creativity

No	Cultivating Scientific Creativity	Mean
1	Encourages students to think innovatively, explore new ideas, and approach scientific challenges with imagination.	3.10
2	Foster scientific creativity by providing opportunities for students to engage in open-ended tasks, design their experiments, and explore scientific phenomena from different perspectives which encourages students to think outside the box and develop unique approaches to problem-solving.	3.20
3	Create a supportive and safe learning environment that values and nurtures students’ ideas and creativity which encourage students to take risks, embrace failure as a learning opportunity, and express their thoughts and hypotheses freely.	3.00
4	Involves incorporating hands-on experiments, inquiry-based activities, and project-based learning into the Science curriculum which allows students to explore their own questions, propose innovative solutions, and engage in scientific discoveries that spark their curiosity and ignite their creativity.	2.10
5	Provide opportunities for students to collaborate, share ideas, and engage in scientific discussions through creating a classroom culture that celebrates diverse perspectives and encourages active participation, teachers inspire students to think creatively and build upon each other’s ideas.	3.40
Overall Mean		2.96

lenges from multiple perspectives. By encouraging students to think creatively, science teachers foster the development of critical thinking skills necessary for scientific inquiry and exploration. Cultivating scientific creativity fosters curiosity and inquisitiveness among students. Research by Beghetto and Kaufman (2018) suggests that when students are encouraged to explore, question, and investigate, their curiosity and intrinsic motivation to learn are heightened. By creating an environment that values curiosity and encourages students to pursue their scientific interests, science teachers nurture a sense of wonder and exploration. Cultivating scientific creativity helps students develop a sense of scientific identity and passion for the subject. Research by Barron et al. (2017) indicates that engaging in creative scientific endeavors enhances students’ sense of ownership, pride, and enthusiasm. By

providing opportunities for students to engage in self-directed projects and pursue their scientific interests, science teachers nurture a love for science and encourage students to pursue scientific careers.

Table 15 shows the summary of the extent of teachers’ facilitation skills across science discipline. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Inquiry-based learning (4.00), and Scaffolding and guided discovery (3.82) are oftentimes manifested, while, Facilitating collaborative learning (3.10), Encouraging critical thinking (2.96), Cultivating scientific creativity (2.96) and Questioning technique (2.80) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.27 denotes that extent of teachers’ facilitation skills across science discipline is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

Table 15. Summary of the extent of teachers’ facilitation skills across science discipline

No	Teachers’ Facilitation Skills Across Science Discipline	Mean
1	Inquiry-based learning	4.00
2	Scaffolding and guided discovery	3.82
3	Questioning technique	2.80
4	Facilitating collaborative learning	3.10
5	Encouraging critical thinking	2.96
6	Cultivating scientific creativity	2.96
Overall Mean		3.27

Teachers’ facilitation skills across the science discipline refer to the abilities and strategies employed by teachers to support and enhance student learning in the field of science. Facilitation skills go beyond traditional teaching methods and involve creating an environment that encourages active participation, critical thinking, collaboration, and inquiry-based learning. Teachers facilitate inquiry-based learning by encouraging students to ask questions, explore scientific phenomena, and develop their own investigations. They guide students in designing experiments, collecting and analyzing data, and drawing conclusions. This approach fosters curiosity, problem-solving skills, and a deeper understanding of scientific concepts. Teachers facilitate collaborative learning by promoting teamwork, communication, and cooperation among students. They create opportunities for students to engage in group activities, discussions, and projects that involve sharing ideas, perspectives, and knowledge. Collaborative learning develops interpersonal skills and exposes students to diverse viewpoints. Teach-

The significant relationship between teachers’ management and facilitation skills across the science discipline is evident in various aspects of effective science teaching. Marzano and Marzano (2003) emphasize the importance of an organized classroom environment

ers facilitate learning by integrating technology into science instruction. They utilize digital tools, simulations, virtual labs, and online resources to enhance students’ access to information, promote data analysis, and provide interactive learning experiences. Technology integration supports inquiry, experimentation, and the exploration of complex scientific concepts.

Significant Relationship between Teachers’ Management And Facilitation Skills Across Science Discipline

It can be depicted that Pearson’s Correlation generated a significant correlation between teachers’ management ($r=0.875$; $p_i.000$) and facilitation skills across science discipline. Table 16 revealed the yielded results of the significant relationship between teachers’ management and facilitation skills across science discipline. It provides an information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant correlation between teachers’ management and facilitation skills across science discipline must be rejected for it provided empirical evidence of significant results.

in supporting instructional planning and implementation. By managing classroom materials and resources efficiently, teachers can create a structured setting that facilitates inquiry-based learning and scientific exploration. Furthermore, the facilitation of active learning and

Table 16. Significant Relationship between teachers’ management and facilitation skills across science discipline

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
teachers’ management facilitation skills across science discipline	0.875	< 0.000	Significant	Reject H_0

**significant @p;0.05.*

inquiry is paramount in science education, as highlighted by the National Research Council (2012). Through thought-provoking questions, hands-on investigations, and student-centered activities, teachers with strong facilitation skills promote critical thinking, problem-solving, and a deeper understanding of scientific concepts. Hands-on experiments and demonstrations play a significant role in science education, and the effective management and facilitation of these activities are essential. Hake (1998) and Windschitl et al. (2012) emphasize the value of hands-on experiences in connecting students with real-world phenomena and enhancing conceptual understanding. Effective management skills ensure that the necessary materials, equipment, and safety measures are in place, while facilitation skills guide students through the process of experimentation and reflection. Collaborative learning is another area where the relationship between management and facilitation skills is evident. Vygotsky’s social constructivism theory emphasizes the importance of collaboration and interaction in learning (Vygotsky, 1978). Johnson et al. (2014) and Gillies (2016) emphasize that teachers who effectively manage group work and facilitate collaborative discussions promote peer-to-peer learning, communication skills, and scientific understanding. By fostering an inclusive and supportive environment, teachers encourage students to engage in meaningful scientific discussions, share ideas, and learn from each other’s perspectives. In conclusion, the relationship between teachers’ management and facilitation skills across the science discipline is significant and intertwined.

Effective management skills enable teachers to create an organized learning environment that supports inquiry-based instruction. Facilitation skills, on the other hand, empower teachers to promote active learning, guide hands-on experiments, and foster collaborative interactions among students. By combining these skills, teachers can create engaging and effective science classrooms where students develop critical thinking, problem-solving abilities, and a life-long passion for scientific inquiry.

On the Domains of Teachers’ Management That Significantly Influence Facilitation Skills Across Science Discipline

Table 17 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on the domains of teachers’ management that significantly influence facilitation skills across science discipline. Domains of teachers’ management in terms of subject knowledge (0.000), planning and organization (0.001), communication (0.000) and technology integration (0.001) significantly influence facilitation skills across science discipline. Meanwhile, classroom management (0.051); differentiation (0.060) and assessment and feedback (0.101) suggest non influential over facilitation skills across science discipline. Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.883 suggests that the domains of teachers’ management, is explained by 88.3%. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (254.897) and F-statistic is significant $p; .001$, tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of the facilitation skills across science discipline.

Table 17. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of teachers’ management that significantly influence facilitation skills across science discipline

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decisions	
H_0	(Intercept)	4.145	0.079	60.416	0.001	4.145
H_1	(Intercept)	0.313	0.175	1.066	0.270	0.204
	SK	0.207	0.107	0.102	1.010	0.315
0.000	*Reject H_0					
	PO	0.241	0.108	0.136	1.299	0.196
0.001	*Reject H_0					
	TI	0.202	0.097	0.210	2.098	0.038
0.000	*Reject H_0					
	CM	0.202	0.097	0.210	2.098	0.038
0.051	Accept H_0					
	D	0.921	0.508	0.136	1.299	0.296
0.060	Accept H_0					
	AF	0.502	0.057	0.210	3.098	0.038
0.101	Accept H_0					
R^2	= 0.893					
F -value	= 254.897					
p -value	= < 0.001					

*Significant

@ $p < 0.05$

SK-Subject knowledge; PO-Planning and organization; C-Communication; CM-Classroom management; D-Differentiation; TI-Technology integration; and AF-Assessment and feedback

The management practices of teachers significantly influence their facilitation skills across the science discipline. Creating a supportive learning environment is paramount in fostering effective facilitation. By establishing clear expectations, routines, and behavior management strategies, teachers create a safe and structured space that promotes student engagement and participation (Brophy, 2006). A well-managed classroom provides a foundation for effective facilitation by minimizing distractions and creating a positive atmosphere where students feel comfortable exploring and asking questions. Furthermore, teachers’ management skills in planning and organization directly impact their facilitation abilities. Through care-

ful lesson planning, teachers can align their instructional goals with appropriate facilitation strategies. Effective management practices allow teachers to structure their lessons effectively, ensuring that they have the necessary resources, materials, and equipment readily available. This organization enables seamless facilitation, as teachers can seamlessly transition between different activities and provide students with hands-on experiences, discussions, and experiments (Varelas et al., 2008). Teachers with strong management skills are also able to effectively manage time and pacing in the science classroom. They allocate sufficient time for each activity, ensuring that students have ample opportunities to engage with scientific concepts,

perform experiments, and reflect on their findings. By managing time effectively, teachers can dedicate adequate attention to facilitating meaningful discussions and addressing student questions, fostering a deeper understanding of scientific principles (Windschitl et al., 2012). Additionally, effective classroom management practices, such as establishing clear expectations for student behavior and academic performance, create a sense of accountability and responsibility. This, in turn, enables teachers to effectively facilitate group work and collaborative activities in the science classroom. Through proper management, teachers can ensure that

students work cooperatively, share ideas, and engage in meaningful discussions (Johnson et al., 2014). In conclusion, teachers' management practices significantly influence their facilitation skills across the science discipline. Creating a supportive learning environment, planning and organizing instructional activities, managing time effectively, and establishing clear expectations all contribute to effective facilitation. By honing their management skills, teachers can optimize their facilitation abilities, fostering a rich and engaging learning experience for students in the science classroom.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusion and recommendation based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and drawn implications. Findings are based on the posed statement of the problem; conclusions are based on the findings generated and recommendations are based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following are findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis and discussions. The extent of teachers' management across science discipline in terms of Communication (3.65) and Assessment and feedback (3.53) are oftentimes manifested, while, Subject knowledge (3.31), Planning and organization (3.19), Technology integration (3.18), Classroom management (3.15) and Differentiation (3.08) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.29 denotes that extent of teachers' management across science discipline is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. The extent of teachers' facilitation skills across science discipline in terms of Inquiry-based learning (4.00), and Scaffolding and guided discovery (3.82) are oftentimes manifested, while, Facilitating collaborative learning (3.10), Encouraging critical thinking (2.96), Cultivating scientific creativity (2.96) and Questioning technique (2.80) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating

of 3.27 denotes that extent of teachers' facilitation skills across science discipline is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between teachers' management ($r=0.875$; $p_i.000$) and facilitation skills across science discipline. Domains of teachers' management in terms of subject knowledge (0.000), planning and organization (0.001), communication (0.000) and technology integration (0.001) significantly influence facilitation skills across science discipline. Meanwhile, classroom management (0.051); differentiation (0.060) and assessment and feedback (0.101) suggest non influential over facilitation skills across science discipline.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are conclusions, to wit; The teachers' management across science discipline in terms of Communication, Assessment and feedback, Subject knowledge, Planning and organization, Technology integration, Classroom management and Differentiation,

ation is moderately extensive. The teachers' facilitation skills across science discipline in terms of Inquiry-based learning, Scaffolding and guided discovery, Facilitating collaborative learning, Encouraging critical thinking, Cultivating scientific creativity and Questioning technique is extensive. There is a significant relationship between teachers' management and facilitation skills across science discipline. Domains of teachers' management in terms of subject knowledge, planning and organization, communication and technology integration significantly influence facilitation skills across science discipline.

4.3. *Recommendations*—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit; Public School District Supervisor. May provide professional development opportunities: District supervisors should prioritize professional development programs that focus on enhancing both management and facilitation skills for science teachers. These programs can include workshops, seminars, and training sessions that provide teachers with the necessary knowledge and strategies to effectively manage their classrooms and facilitate engaging science instruction. Support collaborative planning and reflection: Encourage collaborative planning sessions among science teachers within the district. This allows teachers to share best practices, discuss challenges, and brainstorm innovative ideas for effective management and facilitation. District supervisors can also promote regular reflection sessions to provide teachers with opportunities to evaluate their instructional practices and make necessary adjustments. School Principal. May foster a positive and supportive school culture: School principals should create a positive and supportive school culture that values effective management and facilitation in the science discipline. Recognize and celebrate teachers who

excel in these areas and provide ongoing support and resources to enhance their skills. Allocate resources for science instruction: Ensure that the necessary resources, materials, and equipment are available to support effective facilitation in the science classroom. Collaborate with teachers to identify and prioritize the specific needs for science instruction, and allocate budgetary resources accordingly. Teachers. May continuously develop management and facilitation skills: Teachers should take initiative in improving their management and facilitation skills through professional development opportunities, self-reflection, and seeking feedback from colleagues and administrators. Engage in ongoing learning and stay updated with current best practices in science education. Collaborate and share best practices: Foster a collaborative culture among fellow teachers by sharing successful management and facilitation strategies. Collaborative discussions and peer observations can provide valuable insights and promote professional growth among teachers. Future Researchers. May investigate the impact of specific management strategies on facilitation: Future research should delve into the specific management strategies that have a direct impact on effective facilitation in the science discipline. This can include exploring the relationship between classroom organization, time management, and facilitation techniques, and their influence on student engagement and learning outcomes. Investigate the effectiveness of professional development programs. Conduct research to evaluate the effectiveness of professional development programs that aim to enhance teachers' management and facilitation skills in the science discipline. Investigate the long-term impact of such programs on teacher practices, student learning outcomes, and overall classroom environments.

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